

The Influence Of Vocabulary Mastery On The Ability To Write Explanation Texts Class XI Students of SMA Negeri 3 Depok

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of vocabulary mastery on the ability to write explanatory texts for class XI students of SMA Negeri 3 Depok. The research method used is the type of data collected in the form of quantitative data using data collection on the ability to write explanatory texts for class XI students of SMA Negeri 3 Depok. Based on the data analysis that has been made by students, it is proven that hypothesis testing with a significant level of 5% is obtained ($1.694 > 0.361$), there is an effect of vocabulary mastery on the ability to write explanatory texts and the average explanatory text writing skill is 82.1 higher.

Keywords: Mastery of Vocabulary, Ability to Write Explanatory Text

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the importance of the function of language, both spoken and written, is increasingly felt, which is used to express our ideas and intentions to other people. According to Prihantini (2015: 13-14) language is a system of arbitrary sound symbols, which are used by all people or members of society to work together, interact, identify themselves in the form of good conversation, good behavior and good manners. Language as a means of communication means that humans as social creatures are instinctively driven to associate with other humans, either to express their existence, express their interests, express their opinions, or to influence other people for their own interests, group interests, or common interests. In this regard, language plays a very important role.

What often becomes an obstacle in writing is a lack of mastery of vocabulary, even though vocabulary determines how skilled a person is in language. As stated by Tarigan (2011:2), the quality of a person's language skills clearly depends on the quantity and quality of the vocabulary he has. The richer the vocabulary we have, the greater the possibility that we will be skilled at language. In essence, students have realized that the ability to compose (writing) is a means of communicating in written form. However, you need to know that every time you get a writing assignment, you often experience difficulties. These difficulties can be in the form of difficulty in choosing the right vocabulary, not being able to express the ideas that are in your mind fluently, or not being clear enough in expressing your ideas. One of them is the vocabulary mastery factor.

Vocabulary as an element of language plays an important role in writing activities. Through words, everyone can express thoughts, ideas, knowledge, knowledge and feelings towards other people. This disclosure is realized in the form of articles, short stories or other forms of essays. Writing is a language skill needed to communicate indirectly or not face to face with other people. This writing skill does not come automatically, but must go through practice, quite a lot of practice and of course regularly. The Indonesian language, which continues to grow and develop, of course requires coaching, development and maintenance efforts so that Indonesian becomes a stable and dynamic language. In connection with the above, the function of language is very important as a means of communication both verbally and in writing, but on the other hand we often encounter problems that arise regarding the use of inappropriate vocabulary in a sentence. This does not only happen in certain communities but also in educational

institutions, those who cannot yet use Indonesian well and correctly orally and in writing. If you pay attention, Indonesian language lessons in schools often emphasize only the cognitive aspect, the psychomotor aspect still receives less attention from the language teacher concerned. This is due to the limited time available in face-to-face hours, so teachers often only give assignments to be done at home which should be done during class hours, especially on the subject of writing. With things like this, the mistakes made by students do not receive special attention from the teacher's observations.

High school students, for example, often have difficulty expressing their ideas in essay form (writing). This is due to the tendency for high school students to lack interest (enthusiasm) in reading nowadays, so that vocabulary mastery is very minimal. Often they make mistakes and mistakes in placing vocabulary and terms in sentences and in composing (writing). In addition, the existence of a school library can support and increase students' knowledge horizons to find new information. Teachers are expected to be able to motivate students to enjoy reading to increase their acquisition of vocabulary expressed in sentence structures consisting of several paragraphs.

Language skills require sufficient vocabulary. In other words, a person's vocabulary will also determine the quality of that person's language skills.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is quantitative descriptive. Sugiyono (2013:14) reveals that quantitative descriptive techniques are data analysis techniques based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative or statistics with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. The type of research carried out by the author is quantitative research. Based on this expert's opinion, quantitative research is research that uses data analysis in the form of statistics to test theories based on predetermined hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent characteristics present demographic data for the thirty students who were the research sample as a reference for analyzing the influence of vocabulary mastery on the ability to write explanatory text for class XI students at SMA Negeri 3 Depok. However, please note that the characteristics of respondents in this study only apply to class XI students at SMA Negeri 3 Depok for the 2021/2022 academic year.

Table 1
Frequency Distribution of Students' Vocabulary Mastery
(X Variable)

Nilai	F	Xi	Fi.Xi
60 - 65	19	62,50	1,187,50
66 - 70	4	68,00	272,00
71 - 75	4	73,00	292,00
76 - 80	1	78,00	78,00
81 - 85	1	83,00	83,00
86 - 90	1	88,00	88,00
Jumlah	30		2,000,50

Figure 1
Histogram of Vocabulary Mastery Variables

Thus, the average score obtained through the vocabulary mastery test for class XI students at SMA Negeri 3 Depok was 66.70. From the table above, it can be explained that the vocabulary mastery data is as follows:

Score Minimum : 60
 Shoes maximum : 90
 Rate-rate : 66,70

Table 2
 Frequency Distribution of Students' Explanatory Text Writing Ability
 (Y Variable)

Skor	F	Y	F.Y
65 - 70	1	67,5	67,5
71 - 76	4	73,5	294,0
77 - 82	13	79,5	1.033,5
83 - 88	7	85,5	598,5
89 - 94	3	91,5	274,5
95 - 100	2	97,5	195,0
	30		2.463,0

Figure 2
 Histogram of Variable Ability to Write Explanatory Text

Based on the above, the average score obtained from students from the explanatory text writing test was 82.1. From the table above, it can be explained that the data on the ability to write explanatory text is as follows:

Shoes Minimum : 70
 Maximum Score : 98
 Rata-Rata : 82,1

The benchmark used as a high and low standard of influence between vocabulary mastery (variable)

Table 3
 The level of relationship between word mastery and writing ability

Coefficient Interval	Relationship Level
0,000 – 0,199	Very low
0,200 – 0,399	low
0,400 – 0,599	Currently
0,600 – 0,799	Strong
0,800 – 1,000	Very Strong

As stated in chapter III, the hypothesis formulation that the author proposes is as follows:

H0 : accepted if there is no influence between vocabulary mastery (variable X) on students' ability to write explanatory text (variable Y).

H1 : accepted if there is an influence between vocabulary mastery (variable X) on students' ability to write explanatory text (variable Y).

To prove the two hypotheses, whether H0 or H1 is accepted, the next step is to compare the calculated t with the t table.

Meanwhile, to find the t table, use a confidence level or significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$), two-party test = $n - 2 = 30 - 2 = 28$, so you get a t table = 0.361. After the author determines the results of the t count and t table calculations. It can be seen that the calculated t result is $1.694 > t$ table 0.361 because the calculated t is greater than the t table. So the Ha hypothesis is accepted while H0 is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the influence of vocabulary mastery on the ability to write explanatory text in class XI students at SMA Negeri 3 Depok.

To determine the effect of vocabulary mastery on the ability to write explanatory text, descriptive analysis is used which includes measures of centralization and distribution of data as well as correlation analysis, while hypothesis testing is carried out using inferential analysis which includes calculating t count $>$ t table.

- Descriptively, the research above can be explained as follows: vocabulary mastery of 30 students obtained a minimum score of 60 and a maximum score of 90 with an average of 66.70, while for the ability to write explanatory text a minimum score of 70 and a maximum score of 98 could be obtained with average 82.1.
- From 30 students, the correlation coefficient between vocabulary mastery and the ability to write explanatory text was 0.032. This figure shows that there is a positive correlation with a very low level of relationship (between 0.000 – 0.199) between the variables of vocabulary mastery and the ability to write explanatory text. Vocabulary mastery can explain the variable ability to write explanatory text by 10.29%.
- From the results of calculating the regression equation, it can be concluded that vocabulary mastery tends to have a positive effect on the ability to write explanatory text by 0.54, which means that every time a student's vocabulary mastery increases by 1 unit, the

student's ability to write explanatory text will increase by 0.54 units. To test the hypothesis, it was found that there was a significant influence between vocabulary mastery and the ability to write explanatory text with the result being rejected by H₀.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and hypothesis testing, the author can conclude several things from the results of this research. Vocabulary mastery from 30 students obtained a minimum score of 60 and a maximum score of 90, an average of 66.70. The ability to write explanatory text from 30 students obtained a minimum score of 70 and a maximum score of 98, the average score was 82.1. From 30 students, the correlation coefficient between vocabulary mastery and the ability to write explanatory text was 0.032, which shows that there is a fairly low positive correlation between vocabulary mastery and the ability to write explanatory text. Mastery of vocabulary has an influence on the ability to write explanatory text by 10.29%. To test the hypothesis, it was found that there was an influence between vocabulary mastery on the ability to write explanatory text in class XI students at SMA Negeri 3 Depok. This is based on hypothesis testing with a significance level of 5%, obtained $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($1.694 > 0.361$), then H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted. In this way the hypothesis is tested and significantly accepted.

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